

WORD PREFERENCE OF FEMALE AND MALE IN THE PROCESS OF TRANSLATION

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***Annotation:** This article is concerned with the study of gender aspect in the process of translation. The study focuses on the investigation of the impact of author’s gender on word preference in translation process. To be more specific, the article is aimed to explore the distinctive features of translated work by male and female translators. Previous researches and studies in this area of investigation have been gathered and analyzed. Several points of the issue have been taken into consideration and concluded that there are a number of distinctive differentiations in word preference by male and female translators.*

***Key Words:** Translation, gender, gender identity, male translator, female translator*

The issues related to the influence of the translator’s gender on the translation process remain insufficiently developed. In many cases, the category of “gender” is considered as a linguistic phenomenon, as well as, the realization of the sociocultural aspect in translation studies. The great interest in linguistic translation problems allow us to speak about the formation and development of a new direction in linguistics, linguistics of translation. Experts in this direction consider that the text obtain several functions, including communicative-pragmatic function. The text pragmatics is understood as a communicative aspect which has the ability to cause different associations in the recipient, thereby influencing it.

It is obviously clear that the translator plays a vital role in the process of translation, because he\she creates a new text in the translation language through pragmatic reconstructions of the original text. In that case, the communicative and pragmatic understanding of the translator becomes essential.¹⁶ The foundation of gender studies was the identification of differences in roles, social status and other aspects of life of men and women. The objectification of the male and female view of the world (the gender picture of the world) occurs in written and oral speech, as well as in fiction. With the help of the theory of gender, it is possible to interpret translations of works of fiction in different ways, where author’s view on gender

¹⁶ Chamberlain, I. Gender Metaphorics in Translation, p 82. London: Routledge. 1998.

relations are clearly and deeply embodied. Therefore, differences in the translation of works due to the gender of the translator are in the high interest.

With respect to the difference between genders in language usage in communication and interaction, researches have shown that women and men use language for different reasons in different ways. Maltz and Borker point out that while women use language to create and enhance social relations, men use communication to practice power and dominance.¹⁷ According to Basow and Runenfield, women seem to be more expressive, tentative and polite in conversations and men are more dominant and assertive.

In addition, some scholars argue that linguistic personality of the translator has a vital impact on the process of translation. The linguistic personality of the translator is realized in solving pragmatic tasks as the sender of an artistic text, in choosing such language that provides the emotional impact on the reader corresponding to the original. To solve the problems of such influence, the sender, that is the translator, is consciously or unconsciously guided while playing the text with a certain strategy. The works of fiction are contrasted with all other language works due to the fact that for all of them one of the communicative functions is dominant, namely, artistic and aesthetic. The main goal of any work is to achieve a certain aesthetic influence, the creation of an artistic image. In order to create an artistic and aesthetic image in the brain of reader, translator uses his/her linguistic personality. This property is manifested in the ability of the writer to say more than one word to make both thoughts, feelings and imagination meaningful.

As women are concerned with building close relationships and men are more concerned about maintaining their dominant status, their choice of word varies. In this regards, Lakoff argues that women choose less powerful language as they speak more politely; they swear less than men, and use tag questions more often seeking agreement; he explains that because women speak more tentatively and less assertively than men, they are placed in a position where they are perceived less confident and relatively less powerful. This leaves men, who are not hesitant to use strong and assertive words, in a favorable position of power, dominance and leadership.

Additionally, the text made by women is more figurative than the text of the translation of men, and this effect is achieved by addition of translators reinforcing adjectives or hole speech turns, which makes the translation text much brighter than the original one. This is explained by the fact that at the lexical level, the greatest number of gender features of the translation are manifested. Since women have more

¹⁷Maltz, Daniel N. and Ruth A. Borker. A Cultural Approach To Male-Female Miscommunication. Oxford:Blackwell Publishers: p 417. 1998

than men, the right hemisphere of the brain is developed, they are characterized by imagery of perception and thinking, fantasizing. In female translation words are chosen with connotation.¹⁸

For quite some time gender difference in language use has been an issue that has claimed men and women have different ways of lingual communication. By using research methods, questionnaires and, data analyses it is distinguished that the words and phrases that are preferred by women and men are different in so many ways.

The argument of women and men presenting differences in language use started by daily and casual observations. Nowadays, people who are not related to any scientific research about these issues have the stereotypical idea that women are more polite than men in language use which brings the study back to stereotypical assumptions.

In so many cultures it is stereotypically assumed that women are more polite than men and as a consequence of this stereotypical belief, this assumption leads the growing adolescents to be more polite if they are females and less polite than females if they are males. Moreover, this leads the parents to raise their children based on the stereotypical assumptions too, such as; parents warning their son not to be very polite like a girl which shelters the idea that only females should be kind or parents warning their daughter not to be rude like a man that inside this warning there is the message for people to accept and expect males to be rude. Even sometimes people face tougher situations where they are mocked by the slang words such as fag or tomboy if the way of language use preference of those people do not fit in the stereotypical male or female language use which people are used to. In other words if a man prefers a language use which is more likely for women to use, in some social environments it is not very unlikely for that man not to be mocked or insulted since he embraces a characteristic that belongs to women or vice versa.

To sum up all, when all the information about the subject is taken into consideration, it gives the idea that as there are certain effects of gender in language use, there are some effects of gender in translation works as well. These differences may be minor or sometimes major but this does not mean that all of the translated works have differences because of gender orientation. It is certain that there are some affects as there are some effects of gender in language use as well but it is still an arguable subject whether gender identity causes that major differences. However, it is

¹⁸ Sherry Simon. Gender in Translation: Cultural Identity and The Politics of Transmission, p 96. 1996.

a fact that a translator should be able to keep the language as objective as he can in order to be faithful to the original text.

Reference:

1. Chamberlain, I. Gender Metaphors in Translation, p 82. London: Routledge. 1998.
2. Maltz, Daniel N. and Ruth A. Borker. A Cultural Approach To Male-Female Miscommunication. Oxford:Blackwell Publishers: p 417. 1998
3. Sherry Simon. Gender in Translation: Cultural Identity and The Politics of Transmission, p 96. 1996.